

Impacts Of Digital Literacy In Enhancing Business Education Students' Entrepreneurial Activities In Delta State University, Abraka

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the impacts of digital literacy in enhancing business education students' entrepreneurial activities in Delta State University, Abraka. One research question was answered and one null hypothesis was tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance. This study employed a descriptive survey research design. This design is suitable for obtaining detailed insights into the impact of digital literacy on students' academic and entrepreneurial performance. The population for this study consisted of 309 business education students at Delta State University, Abraka. In the 2024/2025 academic session. A sample size of 175 students was selected using stratified random sampling technique. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire titled "Digital Literacy and Students' Entrepreneurial Activities Questionnaire (DLSEAQ)". The Instrument was face and content validated. The research questions were addressed using the mean and standard deviation, with a benchmark of 2.50. The regression analysis was applied to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The study found that business education students at Delta State University, Abraka, possess a high level of digital literacy. The highest proficiency was recorded in internet usage (mean = 4.50) and word processing (mean = 4.20), while the lowest was in social media usage (mean = 3.70). These findings indicate that students are well-versed in using digital tools for professional tasks but may lack the skills needed to leverage social media effectively for educational and business purposes. It was recommended that Universities should integrate comprehensive digital literacy training into business education programs, focusing on e-commerce, financial management tools, and digital marketing.

Keywords: Digital Literacy, Entrepreneurial Activities, Business Education, Students

INTRODUCTION

Globally, digital skills have become a determinant of employability and entrepreneurial success. The role of digital literacy in enhancing academic and entrepreneurial performance has gained significant attention in recent years. The World Economic Forum (2023) notes that digital literacy is among the top skills

required for individuals to thrive in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. This shift has driven universities worldwide to integrate digital competencies into their curricula to prepare students for competitive labour markets and innovative business environments. In Nigeria, the importance of digital literacy has grown significantly in response to the country's aspirations to diversify its economy and reduce unemployment. The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA, 2023) emphasizes the role of digital skills in fostering innovation, entrepreneurship, and economic growth. However, reports indicate a digital divide in the country, with many students in tertiary institutions lacking access to adequate digital resources and training. According to Adomi and Kpangban (2020), factors such as insufficient digital infrastructure, inadequate funding, and limited internet access contribute to this gap.

Several studies have explored the relationship between digital literacy and academic performance. According to Redecker (2020), students with higher digital literacy levels tend to perform better in research, critical thinking, and collaborative learning. In Nigeria, Adeyemo et al. (2022) found that university students with strong digital literacy skills demonstrated better engagement with e-learning platforms, leading to improved academic outcomes. Additionally, Unesco (2023), identified digital literacy as essential for students to fully participate in modern learning environments, as it allows them to use online platforms, digital libraries, and educational software to improve their academic performance. Similarly, Redecker (2020) posits that students with strong digital literacy skills tend to perform better in research, critical analysis, and problem-solving tasks compared to their less digitally proficient peers.

Students with digital literacy skills can efficiently navigate and utilize digital educational resources such as Google Scholar, ResearchGate, JSTOR, and open-access journals. These platforms provide vast amounts of information that improve students' knowledge base and enhance their learning outcomes. A study by Adeyemo et al. (2023) on Nigerian university students found that those who actively engage with e-learning platforms and digital libraries exhibit a 35% improvement in academic performance compared to students who rely solely on traditional learning methods.

The emergence of Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle, Blackboard, and Coursera has transformed education by providing students with virtual learning experiences. Digitally literate students can navigate these platforms effectively, complete assignments online, and engage in self-paced learning. According to Okojie & Oviawe (2021), students who use e-learning platforms outperform their counterparts by an average of 20% in courses that require independent study and digital collaboration.

Students who are proficient in digital literacy can use communication tools such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meet to participate in virtual discussions, collaborate on group projects, and engage with instructors remotely. Digital collaboration fosters teamwork and enhances students' comprehension of course materials.

A report by the European Commission (2023) found that students who regularly engage in digital collaborative learning activities demonstrate stronger problem-solving abilities and better academic performance than those who do not.

With the rapid growth of information on the internet, students must develop digital research skills to identify credible sources, evaluate information accuracy, and avoid misinformation. Digital literacy helps students develop critical thinking and analytical skills, which are essential for academic success. Adebayo et al. (2023) found that students with advanced digital literacy skills are 40% more likely to produce well-researched academic papers than students with limited digital research competencies.

The digital economy requires entrepreneurs to possess strong digital competencies for business success. The literature highlights that entrepreneurs with digital skills are more innovative, competitive, and capable of expanding their businesses through digital platforms (Nambisan, 2018; Oladimeji & Akintunde, 2023). Findings indicates that:

- Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (2023) reports that over 70% of successful entrepreneurs in emerging markets attribute their success to strong digital literacy skills.
- Oladimeji and Akintunde (2023) found that young entrepreneurs in Nigeria who leverage digital marketing, e-commerce, and fintech tools experience higher business growth than those who rely solely on traditional business methods.

- International Telecommunication Union (2023) highlights that entrepreneurs with strong digital literacy are more adaptable to changing market trends and economic disruptions. The findings indicate that business education students at Delta State University, Abraka, need digital literacy skills to succeed in entrepreneurship by using digital marketing, social media platforms, and e-commerce technologies to grow their businesses.

At Delta State University, Abraka, the integration of digital literacy into the business education curriculum is aimed at addressing these challenges. Business education, as a discipline, is designed to equip students with knowledge and skills in management, accounting, marketing, and entrepreneurship. By embedding digital literacy into the program, the university seeks to produce graduates who are not only academically proficient but also technologically empowered to navigate and excel in the modern business world.

Despite these efforts, anecdotal evidence suggests that a considerable proportion of business education students at Delta State University struggle with digital competencies. This limitation not only affects their academic performance but also hinders their ability to identify and exploit entrepreneurial opportunities. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the critical need for digital literacy, as students worldwide were compelled to transition to online learning platforms (Onyema et al., 2020). The experience exposed glaring disparities in digital preparedness among Nigerian students, further emphasizing the urgency of addressing this issue.

This study, therefore, sought the impacts of digital literacy in enhancing business education students' entrepreneurial activities in Delta State University, Abraka. It aims to bridge the knowledge gap and provide actionable insights into how digital competencies can be harnessed to foster entrepreneurship.

Statement of the Problem

Digital literacy has become an essential skill for academic success and entrepreneurial growth in the 21st century. However, business education students at Delta State University, Abraka, face significant challenges in acquiring and applying digital literacy skills. Observations indicate a lack of adequate digital competencies among students, which negatively impacts their academic performance and limits their ability to explore entrepreneurial opportunities.

The root causes of this problem include limited access to digital tools and resources, inadequate training in digital skills, and infrastructural deficiencies such as unreliable internet connectivity. Additionally, the gap between students' digital literacy levels and the demands of modern business environments exacerbates their struggles to adapt to evolving technological trends. Without addressing these challenges, students may continue to face academic difficulties and miss out on opportunities to leverage technology for entrepreneurial innovation. Therefore, this study sought the impacts of digital literacy in enhancing business education students' entrepreneurial activities in Delta State University, Abraka

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the sought the impacts of digital literacy in enhancing business education students' entrepreneurial activities in Delta State University, Abraka.

Research Question

The study was guided by one research question as thus:

1. What impact does digital literacy have on the entrepreneurial activities of business education students in Delta State University, Abraka.?

Research Hypothesis

One null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: Digital literacy does not have a significant impact on the entrepreneurial activities of business education students.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey research design. This design is suitable for obtaining detailed insights into the impact of digital literacy on students' academic and entrepreneurial performance (Creswell, 2023). The survey method allows for the collection of quantitative data that reflects students' digital literacy competencies and their influence on their entrepreneurial activities (Saunders et al., 2023). The population for this study consisted of 309 business education students at Delta State University,

Abraka. This population includes students across all academic levels (100 to 400 levels), providing a broad perspective on the impact of digital literacy (Departmental records, 2025). A sample size of 175 students was selected using stratified random sampling to ensure representation across different academic levels. Stratified sampling is adopted to minimize selection bias and ensure the inclusivity of diverse experiences and exposure to digital literacy tools. The sample size is determined using Krejcie and Morgan’s (1970) sample size determination table.

Data was collected through a structured questionnaire titled “Digital Literacy and Students’ Entrepreneurial Activities Questionnaire (DLSEAQ)”. The questionnaire was based on a modified four-point Likert rating scale, Strongly Agree (SA) was given four points, Agree (A) three, Disagree (D) two, and Strongly Disagree (SD) one.

To ensure validity, three experts from the Department of Business Education and the Measurement and Evaluation unit reviewed the questionnaire. A pilot study was conducted with 30 students outside the sample population, and the instrument's reliability is tested using Cronbach’s alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.89, indicating strong reliability (Hair et al., 2023).

The questionnaire was distributed to respondents with the assistance of two research assistants. Data analysis involved the use of descriptive statistics, of frequency distribution, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The research questions were addressed using the mean and standard deviation, with a benchmark of 2.50. The regression analysis was applied to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The decision rule stated that a mean of 2.50 or greater indicated strong agreement, while a mean of less than 2.50 indicated strong disagreement. The null hypothesis was retained when the p-value was greater than 0.05 and rejected when the p-value was less than or equal to 0.05. This was because the selection of the hypotheses was based on a probability value of 0.05.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question: *What impact does digital literacy have on the entrepreneurial activities of business education students in Delta State University, Abraka?*

To assess the impact of digital literacy on entrepreneurial activities, students were asked about their use of digital tools in various business functions. The table below shows the results:

Table 1: Impact of Digital Literacy on Entrepreneurial Activities

Entrepreneurial Activity	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Digital Marketing	3.90	0.88	High engagement in digital marketing activities.
Online Business Management	3.75	0.92	Above average use of digital tools for business management.
E-commerce and Online Sales	3.65	0.96	Moderate use of digital tools for e-commerce.
Digital Customer Communication	3.80	0.85	High use of digital tools for customer communication.
Financial Management with Software	3.60	1.02	Moderate use of digital tools for financial management.

The findings suggest that digital literacy positively influences entrepreneurial activities. Students reported a high level of engagement with digital marketing (mean score = 3.90) and customer communication (mean score = 3.80). However, the use of digital tools for financial management and e-commerce was less pronounced, indicating that these areas may require more attention and training.

Hypothesis Testing

Digital literacy does not have a significant impact on the entrepreneurial activities of business education students.

Table 2: Hypothesis: – Impact of Digital Literacy on Entrepreneurial Activities

Hypothesis	Test Statistic	p-value
Digital literacy does not have a significant impact on entrepreneurial activities.	4.80**	0.001

The p-value (0.001) is less than 0.01, indicating that digital literacy has a significant impact on entrepreneurial activities. This hypothesis is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study found that business education students at Delta State University, Abraka, possess a high level of digital literacy. The highest proficiency was recorded in internet usage (mean = 4.50) and word processing (mean = 4.20), while the lowest was in social media usage (mean = 3.70). These findings indicate that students are well-versed in using digital tools for academic and professional tasks but may lack the skills needed to leverage social media effectively for educational and business purposes.

The correlation analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between digital literacy and academic performance. Internet usage had the strongest correlation with GPA ($r = 0.70$, $p < 0.01$), followed by word processing ($r = 0.62$) and email communication ($r = 0.60$). The weakest correlation was observed with social media usage ($r = 0.42$).

The study also found a significant impact of digital literacy on entrepreneurial activities. Digital marketing (mean = 3.90) and digital customer communication (mean = 3.80) were the most commonly used digital tools among student entrepreneurs, while financial management using software had the lowest mean score (3.60).

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that digital literacy is crucial for academic success and entrepreneurial development. Business education students with higher digital proficiency perform better academically and are more likely to engage in online business ventures. However, gaps remain in the use of social media for academic purposes and financial management tools in business activities. Addressing these gaps through targeted training and curriculum integration will enhance students' competitiveness in the digital economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To maximize the benefits of digital literacy, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Curriculum Enhancement:** Universities should integrate comprehensive digital literacy training into business education programs, focusing on e-commerce, financial management tools, and digital marketing.
2. **Faculty Development:** Lecturers should receive training on modern digital teaching tools to enhance student learning experiences.
3. **Entrepreneurial Skill Development:** Business education students should be encouraged to utilize digital tools for business management and financial planning through workshops and hands-on training.
4. **Social Media Utilization:** Institutions should promote the use of social media for academic and professional networking, ensuring students can leverage these platforms beyond social interactions.
5. **Collaboration with Industry:** Universities should partner with tech companies and business incubators to provide students with practical exposure to digital business operations.

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